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Design and Optimization of a Compliant Morphing Trailing Edge for High-Lift Generation

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Abstract: This work focuses on the design and optimization of a morphing-compliant system developed within the project HERWINGT (Clean Aviation) and aimed at generating high lift during take-off and landing. The device was conceived to replace a conventional flap of a regional aircraft and work in synergy with a droop nose and a flow control system. The architecture is based on a compliant layout, specifically selected to obtain a final morphed shape of the trailing edge of the wing efficient for high-lift purposes and adequately smooth even in cruise clean configuration. At first, the requirements at aircraft level were critically examined and then elaborated to produce the specifications of the morphing device. A layout was then sketched, considering on its potential in approaching the target morphed shape and on its intrinsic criticalities. Starting from this scheme, a simplified FE model was introduced. The scope was to have an efficient predictive tool suited for optimization processes. After having identified the most relevant design parameters (skin thickness distribution, topology of the structure, and actuator interface parameters), the cost function, and the constraints of the problem (structural integrity and stability), a genetic optimization was implemented. Repeating the genetic process starting from different initial populations, some optimized configurations were identified. A trade-off was thus organized on different criteria, such as the lightness of the structure, the load-bearing capability, the force, and the stroke needed by the actuator. The best compromise was finally taken as baseline for the realization of an advanced FE model used to validate the numerical outcomes obtained during the optimization process and as starting point for the next steps planned in the project. The achieved design is characterized by an enhanced aerodynamic performance with the absence of steps and gaps and external track fairings, reduced weight of both the structure and the actuator, reduced maintenance costs due to a simple layout, and smaller take-off and landing distances owing to the high-lift capability and the intrinsic lightness.

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1. Introduction

The aerospace sector is experiencing rapid growth strictly related to some specific factors, such as the market entry of emerging countries as China and India [1,2], the increase in the e-commerce demand for fast and efficient shipments [3], and the evolution of geopolitical situations (wars, pandemics, etc.) altering the conventional trade routes and demanding new ones [4]. All these aspects dramatically affect the environment and climate through dramatic increase in the emission of pollutants [5,6]. Many strategies are under investigation to mitigate this problem. A critical role is played by emerging technologies. In this sense, the next generation of sustainable aviation fuels (SAF) is doing well [7,8]: hydrogen and biofuels are increasingly taking the spotlight despite the challenges that must be faced [9]. Electric propulsion is another strategic technology for the abatement of chemical emissions and acoustic nuisances and for its versatility in the different on-board systems [10–12]. Other interesting technologies are the natural laminar flow [13–15] and the morphing of aerodynamic surfaces [16–18], both having an impact in terms of efficiency improvement of the aircraft.

Several studies have been conducted on novel technologies and aircraft configurations [19,20]. The interest in morphing systems' targeting flow control is widespread in the scientific environment, essentially for the benefits that can be achieved. Among them is the investigation of the unsteady flow behavior of a NACA 0012 airfoil integrated with a bio-inspired morphing trailing edge flap, whose findings indicated that the proposed system can lead to instantaneous lift increases [21]; the numerical study on a flexible leading edge mounted on a NACA 0012 configuration whose actuation led to an increase in the lift coefficient of up to 15% and a reduction in the drag coefficient of up to 10% [22]; the optimization design of a morphing flap for an A320 A/C based on shape-memory alloy technology, providing an architecture capable of replacing a conventional flap [23]; and the numerical predictions about the impact of morphing systems on the take-off and landing performance of the same A/C [24]. A crucial role is played by the identification of the structural architecture matching the prescribed morphed shape. Due to the complexity of the problem, dedicated topology optimization strategies are under investigation; the most common approaches are the variable density and level set methods [25]. The problem of searching for an optimal configuration starting from a pre-defined layout of 1D elements whose edges and thickness can be suitably modified is related to variable density [26]. In this case, the position of the edges can be changed among discrete values. Some examples of topology optimization of morphing structures can be found in [27], where the inner structure of a full-sized morphing trailing edge was sought, or in [28], addressing the topology optimization of a leading and trailing edge.

In the last decades, one may distinguish three main waves of funding/action program at the worldwide and European level.

The Smart Wing Project (1995–2001) and Morphing Aircraft Structures (MAS) (2003–2007) of DARPA [29,30] and the European 5th and 6th Framework Programmes (1998–2002 and 2002–2006) [31,32] belonged to the first exploratory wave (late 1990s through the early years of the twenty-first century). The Electric Aircraft Propulsion (EAP) phase 1 (2010–2015) [33] and the Adaptive Compliant Trailing Edge (ACTE) (2014–2018) [34] of NASA as well as the Continuous Lower Energy, Emissions, and Noise (CLEEN) Program, phases 1–2 (2010–2020) [35], were promoted by the FAA and the 7th Framework Programme (2007–2015). The Clean Sky and Clean Sky 2 programs (2008–2014 and 2014–2020) [36,37]

belonged to the second wave of actions, focusing on the selection of the most promising technologies and on their integration. Finally, the next phases of the already-cited programs of Electric Aircraft Propulsion, phases 2–5 (2015–2025), and Continuous Lower Energy, Emissions, and Noise, phases 3–4 (2020–2030), at the U.S. level and the Clean Aviation program (2022–2028) [38] at the EU level are part of the third-wave actions and generally concern the extension of the selected technologies to full-sized structures for a pre-industrial or industrial use.

The Project Hybrid Electric Regional Wing Integration Novel Wing Technologies (HERWINGT), given in ref. [39], is supported by the above-mentioned Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking Programme. HERWINGT will validate, down-select, mature, and demonstrate the concept, the architecture, the design, and the key technologies for addressing an innovative wing design of a hybrid electric regional aircraft (HER) with a maximum capacity of 100 seats and a range from 500 to 1000 km. The aim is a reduction in CO₂ and other greenhouse (GHG) emissions by improving the aerodynamic efficiency and reducing the weight of the wings of future aircrafts.

The development of a morphing trailing edge represents a significant advancement in aerodynamics and aircraft performance, particularly during critical phases of flight, such as take-off and landing [40]. HERWINGT [41], amongst others, pursues the objective of enabling the activation of wing camber morphing to generate high lift during the take-off and landing phases. To achieve that, a compliant morphing architecture capable of generating high lift when activated and reducing drag owing to the absence of steps and gaps in clean configuration [42] has been properly conceived. This is assured by a dedicated design and integration of a continuous skin that ensures the optimal aerodynamic shapes are maintained while adhering to certification regulations. The use of a continuous surface minimizes turbulence and drag and, at the same time, maximizes lift, contributing to overall aerodynamic efficiency [43]. Another aim relevant to the proposed morphing trailing edge technology is the integration of electro-mechanical actuation (EMA) systems, capable of robustly withstanding sizing loads without compromising performance or safety. Finally, the design, manufacturing, and ground testing of a true-scale segment of the compliant device are other essential objectives. The proposed architecture will replace an inner flap spanning 3.8 m and an outer tapered flap spanning 6.6 m. In addition, a single-bay assembly with a limited span of 0.5 m is also foreseen for the mentioned ground demo purposes.

Different configurations were investigated for the above-mentioned compliant morphing trailing edge. This paper focuses on a specific layout derived from lessons learned by the architectures previously explored. The final scope of the activities described in what follows is the design of the morphing-compliant training edge segment prototype with a span of 0.5 m.

First, the requirements at aircraft level are presented, highlighting their impact on the investigated device. This process ends with the translation of these requirements into specifications for the specific technology. On this basis, the layout of the system is identified, also considering the lessons learned from two previous architectures. After freezing the layout comes the design task. To this scope, a genetic approach was implemented, trying to determine the best compromise amongst different, often conflicting requirements approaching the target morphed shape, the structural integrity, the compliance with actuation capabilities, and the weight. A light finite-element model of the system was realized to reduce the computational effort related to the evaluation of several configurations. This model was conceived to quickly address static, buckling, and modal analyses by altering some critical design parameters, such as the skin thickness distribution, the topology of the architecture, and the transmission features of the actuation chain. Then, after good candidate was identified, a more refined finite-element model was realized with the aim of both

verifying the predictions obtained through the light optimization model and better describing the working of the system, in view of a future realization of a prototype for laboratory tests. Finally, the predicted performance was critically analyzed and compared with the requirements to highlight potential deviations and identify possible room for improvement. The paper is organized in the following sections based on the described approach:

- The present introduction, offering an overview of the scientific scenario in which the work was undertaken;
- A paragraph devoted to the requirements and specifications, linking the objective at A/C level to the main expected features of the morphing system;
- A section to introduce the proposed architecture, its genesis, and working modality;
- A paragraph devoted to the preliminary design and optimization of the concept, concluding with a trade-off among the most significant solutions,
- A section illustrating the advanced design of the concept with focus on the achieved performance;
- A recap section tracking a comparison between the specifications and the achievements of the design;
- A concluding paragraph to give an overview of the contents of the paper and the main results, recalling the further steps of the research.

The outcomes of this study will be exploited in the next part of the project to build a full-sized segment of the morphing trailing edge intended to be tested on the ground.

Due to the multidisciplinary nature of the final product, involving competencies in terms of the definition of requirements at the A/C level and specifications at the system level, structural design of conventional and unconventional parts, kinematic chain simulation, actuation sizing, and optimization integration, the synergic cooperation of three main contributors was necessary:

- CIRA, in charge of developing the aero-structural design of the compliant morphing flap at A/C and DEMO level;
- Collins Aerospace, for the actuation and control system of the MF at aircraft level;
- Leonardo, for the main supervision of all the previous actions and steering the product towards the industrial application.

The harmonization of the competencies above led to the definition of an innovative architecture meeting specific requirements and paving the way for future industrial applications. The innovation of this work does not stand in the algorithms and tools used but in the identification of a concept for potentially replacing a conventional high-lift system, offering advantages in multiple directions: aerodynamic, load absorption, lightness, and maintenance operations. To yield this result, tailored criteria for selection were identified and modulated in the optimization task. Finally, as will be clarified in the next part of the paper, the proposed layout can be considered as an evolution of other two, implementing their most interesting aspects in terms of simplicity of the architecture, lightness, and capability of absorbing loads.

2. Requirements and Specifications

The top-level aircraft requirements (TLAR) for HERWINGT were identified by Leonardo Aircraft (LDO) with respect to a baseline configuration consisting of a conventional ATR72-like aircraft. The overall target is a reduction of 15% in fuel emission, broken down into a 12% improvement of the aerodynamic efficiency, 3% reduction in the weight, and 1% decrease in the off-take power. These requirements can be translated to the wing level in 12%, 20%, and 50%, respectively, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Requirements at wing and aircraft level.

In this scenario, two high aspect-ratio wings were designed. CIRA in particular created the aero-structural design of a cantilever wing [2], while a truss-braced wing architecture design and final MD optimization were created by Politecnico di Milan (PoliMi). Technical University of Delft (TUD) performed detailed wing aerodynamic and structural sizing. The wings were subject to a trade-off analysis by Leonardo Aircraft by comparing the aerodynamic performance in cruise and climb conditions as well as the structural analysis and weight. Finally, the truss-braced high-aspect ratio wing was selected as representative of the wing configuration investigated in HERWINGT.

The requirements relevant to the high-lift system, comprising the combination of a morphing droop nose, an adaptive trailing edge, and an active flow control, were specified by Leonardo Aircraft and can be summarized as follows:

1. Enhanced Aerodynamic Performance: The movable parts devoted to the high-lift generation, morphing trailing edge, and droop nose must assure a clean configuration in cruise condition, without any steps and gaps when retracted [43];
2. Weight Reduction in Actuation Systems: Due to the integration of the actuation system within the structure, constrained by a lack of deployment systems and external fairings, a weight reduction of approximately 10% is expected at the A/C level. This requirement, with specific reference to the morphing trailing edge, means a weight lower than 22 kg/m, including actuation;
3. Shorter Take-off Distances: The advanced high-lift system allows for a reduction in take-off distances of around 9%. This capability enables aircraft to operate from shorter runways, enhancing operational flexibility;
4. Improved Landing Roll Efficiency: The implementation of this system may result in a 6% reduction in landing roll distances, which not only enhances safety but also decreases wear on runway surfaces and brakes [44].

The high-lift flow is characterized by a velocity of 130 KTAS at zero altitude, resulting in a Mach number of 0.20 and Reynolds number per unit length of 4.58×10^6 L/m. The requirements for high-lift performance, formulated at the aircraft level in the framework of the Clean Aviation HERA Project, are $C_{L,MAX} = 2.6$ in take-off and 2.8 in landing conditions, respectively. Some numerical assessments based on engineering methods were performed in order to evaluate the 3D-to-2D scaling factor. The result was about 0.8 and was confirmed by lattice Boltzmann-based physics CFD simulations. These figures have a critical impact on the requirements of the take-off and landing distances and thus are used as standard of comparison in this work.

This augmented high lift is produced by the aerodynamic configuration shown in Figure 2, suited for the truss-braced wing sketched in Figure 3 and aimed at significantly enhancing the lift capacity of an aircraft, particularly during critical phases of flight, such as

take-off, landing, and low-speed maneuvering. It is achieved through advanced design features that optimize airflow, minimize drag, and adapt the aerodynamic profile dynamically. To this scope, the SU2 open-source RANS flow solver was used [45]. Two flaps contribute to generation of the high lift, namely the inner and outer flaps (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Target morphed shape including the synergic implementation of the droop nose effect and of the chamber morphing.

Figure 3. High-lift morphing devices configuration as selected by trade-off studies.

The target morphed shape produces the lift coefficient illustrated in the plot of Figure 4 together with the one in the clean configuration.

The structure enabling high-lift conditions must meet different specifications due to stringent aeronautical regulations and safety standards. The aerodynamic profile must maintain its shape during both deformed and undeformed phases under external loads. Shape integrity must be ensured to a specific safety level and guaranteed by adherence to a safety factor (SF) greater than 1. Additionally, the first resonance frequencies must be sufficiently low to avoid flutter phenomena. All these requirements must also ensure that the overall weight of the structure is at least 10% less than that of a conventional flap system.

Figure 4. Lift coefficient vs. AoA for clean configuration (2D computation).

Another crucial aspect is represented by the layout, the geometry, and the materials of the parts for the impact in terms of maintenance and reliability. The selected architecture shall be characterized by the following:

- Easy inspection and accessibility; in this sense, configurations with a relatively small amount of parts and based on a modular approach will be privileged; moreover, the organization and the position of the parts shall also be defined to favor the removal of damaged parts minimizing the access operations (removal of additional components); this criterion will be also matched by the actuator and relevant kinematic transmission chain;
- Parts with geometry easily obtainable through conventional manufacturing techniques and linkable to each other using common integration approaches (e.g., riveting, bonding, and bolting);
- Materials commonly used in aeronautics, such as typical metallic alloys and composite layups.

Finally, the requirements for an actuator to support the different high-lift surfaces are summarized below:

- Operation time of approximately 15 s;
- Load at actuator interface with the morphing architecture, including friction load and a margin of 1.5:
 - o Greater than 1500 N for the 0.5 m spanned trailing edge; this requirement will be specifically considered for the demonstrator object of this work;
 - o Greater than 11,000 N for the 3.8 m spanned inboard trailing edge;
 - o Greater than 20,000 N for the 6.6 m spanned tapered outboard trailing edge.

3. The Proposed Architecture

The compliant trailing edge investigated in this work is constituted by an upper and lower skin panel with a stepwise variable thickness. As shown in the bottom scheme of

Figure 5, a web element connects these two panels for cooperation in absorbing loads. The thickness distribution of the skin parts and the web and the position of the web itself is the result of a good compromise among different requirements in terms of structural integrity, lightness, shape preservation under the external actions, and approaching the target morphed shape shown in Figure 2.

Figure 5. Evolution of the configuration design of the morphing trailing edge: truss rib configuration, C_1 , X-Rib configuration, C_2 , and hybrid configuration, C_3 .

The actuation subsystem comprises a linear actuator hinged on the front edge and connected on the other edge to the lower skin through a flange. The pulling action of the actuator is transmitted to the lower skin, whose retraction determines the bending of the trailing edge.

Starting from the definition of the requirements discussed in the previous section, an initial 2D aerodynamic assessment was carried out to obtain aerodynamic shapes and loads. The aerodynamic data were concurrently used as input for two distinct configurations, designated as C_1 and C_2 , which were designed and evaluated as structural layouts with actuation systems through industrial collaboration with Collins concerning the actuation elements. This thorough concept selection drove the creation of a new third configuration, C_3 , integrating the best features of the previous ones.

For all three configurations, a compliant architecture was chosen to enable wing morphing capabilities. This decision was driven by the inherent advantages of compliant morphing devices, capable of exhibiting precise deformation of sub-components to seamlessly alter the overall shape of the assembly. The structural stiffness is carefully designed to provide the necessary compliance for substantial deformations while ensuring adequate robustness to maintain a defined shape under external aerodynamic pressures.

As mentioned, the first architecture investigated, namely C_1 (Figure 5, top left), is a truss rib configuration composed of a one-piece composite morphing skin and equipped with a lower strip portion capable of sliding in the chordwise direction under the action of a linear actuation system [46]. Two morphing ribs, with selective stiffness truss elements

properly attached to the skin, allow the morphed-down activation under the actuation loads action.

The second layout, namely C_2 , accounts for an X-Rib configuration (Figure 5, top right). It was conceived to optimize the number of linear actuators from two to one through genetic algorithms. The morphed-down shape is achieved through a push-and-pull linear actuation system [46].

Both these architectures proved their ability in approaching the target morphed shape. Despite this capability, efforts were spent to arrive at an architecture characterized by a simplified layout to achieve easier integration and maintenance processes and implement the lesson learned from the previous architectures in terms of load absorption.

The final configuration, C_3 , or hybrid configuration (Figure 5, bottom), is equipped with two external linear actuators (heritage from C_1) in line with the left and right border rib planes; a vertical web (heritage from C_2) was inserted to guarantee torsional absorption. The demonstrator version spanning 0.5 m is, however, equipped with only one actuator at mid-span performing the same action of the above-mentioned two external lateral ones. As mentioned above, this architecture is driven by ease of integration and maintenance. The inner structure is cut to the bone with a unique web reinforcing the upper and lower skin panels and driving their relative motion. The design allows easier access to the narrow space and a more efficient replacement of the damaged parts.

The idea at the basis of configuration C_3 is to produce a bending down of the skin, pulling the bottom edge by means of linear actuators. From a structural point of view, the forward edge of the top skin is clamped to the wing box interface, while the corresponding forward edge of the bottom skin is directly connected to the actuation kinematic chain. This assembly drives the forward movement of the bottom skin through dedicated tracks and, at the same time, represents itself as a structural constraint. The web contributes to the absorption of the loads—particularly shear loads—practically splitting the structure in two cells.

The layout assures that a smooth deflection through the most critical part from the aerodynamic point of view—the upper skin—is bent down without any geometric discontinuity; the lower skin is deflected without any instability risk, as no shortening is required but instead just sliding the forward portion. Moreover, even if the slide zone is in principle a discontinuity region, its location from an aerodynamic point of view is less critical, and technical solutions (elastomeric sealing, f.i.) can be considered to further mitigate the problem.

A ball-screw actuator for the operation of the morphing trailing edge was identified. Combined with a linear guidance system and mechanical transmission, this technology offers a complete solution for managing movement and synchronization in demanding environments while ensuring optimal control of aerodynamic surfaces. This actuation architecture identified by Collins Aerospace France and U.K. can be centralized or distributed. It is inherently irreversible or prone to the use of active power-off brakes.

The ball-screw actuator system proposed by Collins Aerospace is based on a screw-nut mechanism, where a rotary movement (provided by an electric motor) is transformed into a linear movement. The linear guide maintains the path parallel to the lower surface, preventing any misalignment when activating the system. The mechanical transmission connected to the actuators synchronizes the movements of all the aerodynamic surfaces whether they are inboard, outboard, or located on either side of the blade. The combination of these technologies allows for quick adjustments, adapting to the conditions of use of the high-lift morphing trailing edges. This prevents any unintentional movement of the mechanism in the event of a mechanical failure. Moreover, the transmission ensures that all the movable parts maintain their relative positions, with no misalignment between

them. The synchronization of movements reduces asymmetric effects, minimizing the risk of structural deformations. Aerospace environments impose severe stresses, such as temperature variations, continuous vibrations, and wing box deflection and prolonged exposure to dynamic loads. The ball–screw system, linear guidance, and mechanical transmission meet these challenges with a robust design that can withstand these high mechanical loads. The mechanical transmission ensures perfect coordination of the movable parts, even under extreme conditions. This solution also allows for a reduction in overall weight, as it is intrinsically lighter than hydraulic alternatives.

Despite the above-mentioned advantages, some critical aspects must be discussed. First is the stress accumulation due to the compliant nature of the system [46], to which some regions seem particularly critical, such as the clamp of the upper skin, the web connections, and the sliding region on the lower skin. An accurate design must accomplish the stress mitigation task for these parts to assure an adequate safety and fatigue life. Another crucial aspect is represented by the actuators; since, in this specific layout, the actuation must cooperate with the structure in absorbing loads, any fault would have a potential impact not only in terms of functionality but also in terms of structural integrity. In addition, the sliding track system must be carefully sized to avoid both friction/jamming issues and the triggering of unwanted vibratory phenomena. Last but not the least is the instability. Although the sliding mode of the lower skin prevents any instability relevant to the shortening of the skin, its rigidity and the layout must together assure an adequate behavior under the external loads avoiding collapse while keeping the desired shape.

4. Design Approach and Optimization

The development of the above-mentioned C_3 concept was addressed by means of the FE approach. As shown in Figure 6, the process was split in two main steps: a first step devoted to the identification of the main design parameters of the architecture and its optimization and a second step focusing on the advanced design and on the validation of the results previously obtained. The FE simulations were addressed by means of the MSC NASTRAN 2024.1 solver; the FEMAP v11.3.2 pre- and post-process software were also used to realize, analyze, and present the results for both the simplified and advanced models. To assure an adequate level of detail, the DMU of the advanced design was realized by means of the CATIA v5 CAD software. Finally, the optimization was addressed by means of an in-house genetic algorithm in the MATLAB R2020b environment.

The design and optimization of the system was carried out through a genetic algorithm. The core of the algorithm was defined to estimate the functionality and the load absorption capability of a generic layout of the morphing device. For each configuration processed by the algorithm, the flowchart shown in Figure 7 was implemented. It describes the following:

- A static analysis to estimate the stress level, the force needed by the actuation, the deflection that can be achieved through a certain layout, and the impact of the external loads on the initial and final configurations;
- A buckling analysis to exclude any instability determined by the external loads;
- A normal mode analysis: Even if the proposed system cannot be classified as a dynamic device like an aileron, to assure an adequate rigidity and exclude any undesired coupling phenomenon, a normal mode analysis is also required to verify that the lowest modal frequency is higher than a threshold.

Figure 6. Design process.

Figure 7. Flow chart of the core of the genetic algorithm.

An important role in the computation of the fitness is played by the deviation, D , along the curvilinear abscissa, s . Then, the stress level, the 1st buckling eigenvalue, and 1st normal mode are also considered, enforcing the algorithm to privilege configurations with values over the thresholds.

The fitness, in line with the considerations above, is computed as product of four terms:

- The factor f_D , which is the inverse of the summation of the deviation, D , along the curvilinear abscissa, over the maximum of the abscissa;
- The factor f_s equal to 1 or 0.1 depending on whether the maximum von Mises stress is less than or greater than 200 MPa;
- The factor f_λ equal to 1 or 0.1 depending on whether the 1st buckling eigenvalue, λ , is greater than or lower than 1.1;
- The factor f_ω equal to 1 or 0.1 depending on whether the 1st normal frequency, ω , is greater than or lower than 40 Hz.

The values assumed by the above factors were chosen to privilege the best-performing configurations and, at the same time, preserve the heritage of the other configurations. In greater detail, a single unsatisfactory condition penalizes by the order of 1 the probability of heritage transmission. This penalization progressively arises if other conditions are not satisfied. The structure and the behavior of the fitness function must meet the main requirements of the morphing device, in terms of shape fitting, robustness, and interaction with other the wing-supporting structure. A threshold of 200 MPa for the stress level was chosen for the factor f_s to guarantee the fatigue tolerance capability of the compliant structure made of 7075-T6 aluminum alloy. A small margin of 10% was then selected with respect to the 1st eigenvalue for the instability part of the fitness function, f_λ ; this assumption, supported by the outcomes of preliminary investigations leading to an instability direction opposite to the operational loads, was then confirmed by the advanced design. Finally, the condition on the frequency of 40 Hz meets more needs: (1) avoiding any potential coupling with the wing-supporting structure subjected, among the others, to the aileron solicitation (up to 20 Hz); (2) mitigating any coupling with the test rig that will be used in the next part of the research for static and dynamic validation; and (3) being compliant with potential future testing in wind tunnel facilities.

Other parameters were not included in the optimization loop: the structural weight and the actuation force and stroke. Since the chosen layout is already characterized by an intrinsic lightness and simplicity, the weight parameter was relaxed in favor of the robustness, thus yielding a wider range of solutions. Finally, with the intention of focusing on the compliant part of the system, the actuation features were not considered in this phase; however, a preliminary sensitivity study on the present layout confined the force and stroke of the actuator within a reasonable range compliant with the requirements. Then, it is worth noting that weight and actuation force and stroke impact were considered in the trade-off phase organized among the optimized solutions that confirmed the assumption on the ranges.

Although the previously mentioned types of analyses are linear and thus relatively light, their repetition for thousands of configurations within an optimization process can significantly increase the computation times.

To streamline the process, the simplified FE model shown in Figure 8 was thus specifically realized. The skin panels and the web were modeled through a total of 221 beam elements. To take into account the span dimension, a width of 0.5 m was set for the cross-section of each elements. A part of these elements, 200, were used for the upper and lower skin panels. This amount assures an adequate discretization both in terms of displacement and stress computation (element extension of about 5 mm over a skin chord of 0.5 m) and, at the same time, allows a satisfactory distribution of aerodynamic loads, matching the original trend of the pressure on 100 stations per panel. The 20 remaining beam elements were used for the web. This amount of elements provided an adequate discretization of the displacement and stress field on the component. The thickness and materials were fixed to be the same of the original architecture; the actuator and its connection to the lower skin were realized by rigid elements. The pulling action was modeled by means of

RBE2 elements contracting by a fictitious expansion coefficient and thermal load. According to the operational modality, the edge point of the beam-like upper panel was clamped. This constraint was chosen to take into account the continuation of the panel with its corresponding portion on the wing box further reinforced by the connection with the inner interface cap of the wing box. In addition, the seven nodes of the beam-like lower panel close to the actuator connection were constrained to slide along the skin tangent, according to the local reference frame highlighted in the figure; the actuator was then pinned on the forward edge. A static analysis of this model takes 5–8 s using a i7-8665U CPU at 1.9 GHz, with 16 Gb of RAM.

Figure 8. Simplified FE model released for the optimization.

The above-mentioned in-house genetic algorithm was used [47]. As shown in the flow chart of Figure 9, an initial population is randomly generated. Each individual is defined by a layout of a certain typology plus the thickness distribution of the skin and the web. Each geometric and thickness property constitutes a single chromosome of the individual. A first fitness evaluation is performed using the core scheme discussed above. On this basis, a classification is built. Then, a new population is created privileging the individuals with the higher fitness but at the same time not discharging the lowest one; a crossover operation is executed, randomly exchanging 50% of the chromosomes between individuals. At this point, to avoid any premature convergences, a mutation, i.e., the random alteration of some parts of the genetic heritage of some individuals, is also performed. The new population is again processed to find the current fitness distribution. These steps (crossover, mutation, fitness evaluation, and assessment of a new population) are repeated until, after 50 iterations, no increase in the maximum fitness value is observed. More optimization processes were repeated, starting from different initial populations to further avoid the risk of premature convergences and to address a final trade-off among the best individuals.

In Table 1, the parameters of the optimization model, their typology (that is to say, if they are subjected to the optimization or not), and the range are reported. The actuator location and length are determined by the position of its forward hinge, assuming that it is initially parallel to the forward sliding region of the lower skin segment. The location of the web is defined by the identification number of the nodes of the upper and lower skin to which it is connected. The thickness of the web was assumed uniform and defined through a dedicated parameter. To have a major chance of adaptation to the target shape, a stepwise thickness distribution for the upper and lower skin was considered; this was defined by a total of six parameters: with reference to Figure 8, two parameters for the thickness values of the upper and lower skin fore regions, two for the corresponding rear regions, and another two defining the identification numbers of the nodes bordering the rear and fore regions.

Figure 9. Algorithm flowchart.

Table 1. Parameter setting for genetic optimization.

Parameter Id (*)	Parameter Description	Type	Range	Notes	
P ₁	Actuator forward hinge—abscissa	Optimization parameter	[−0.25 .. −0.10], m	Point A in Figure 8; global reference frame Point B in Figure 8; progressive Id from 1 (top skin clamped node) to 101 (trailing edge) Point C in Figure 8; progressive Id from 102 (bottom skin forward edge) to 201 (node immediately upstream of the trailing edge)	
P ₂	Actuator forward hinge—ordinate		[0.04 .. 0.15], m		
P ₃	Top connection node of the web		[12 .. 83], node Id		
P ₄	Bottom connection node of the web		[115 .. 184], node Id		
P ₅	Web thickness		[0.3 .. 3.0], mm		
P ₆	Upper skin thickness—forward region		[1.0 .. 3.0], mm		See highlighted region in Figure 8
P ₇	Upper skin thickness—rearward region				
P ₈	Lower skin thickness—forward region				
P ₉	Lower skin thickness—rearward region				
P ₁₀	Upper skin extension—forward region				
P ₁₁	Lower skin extension—forward region		[102 .. 201], node Id		Rear edge of the lower skin forward region; point E in Figure 8
NA	Skin material	Fixed parameter	7075-T6 Aluminum alloy	See [48] for the mechanical properties considered	
	Web material		Rigid	RBE2 element [49]	
	Actuator connection to the lower skin		Rigid	A fictitious thermal expansion coefficient of $-0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ was assumed to simulate the contraction; the fictitious thermal load was estimated to obtain the target trailing vertical displacement	
	Actuator		Rigid		

(*) No Id was assigned to the fixed parameters.

For the external aerodynamic loads, the most severe condition was considered. This condition refers to the fully actuated morphing trailing edge (see green line in Figure 2) at a speed of 90 m/s at sea level with load factor 2. The pressure coefficient distribution along the airfoil is plotted in Figure 10; highlighted in yellow is the trailing edge region. The Euler simulation was performed because the absence of flow separation ensures higher aerodynamic loads, leading to a more conservative approach. The results by the well-known Xfoil [50] code are also reported for sake of comparison.

Figure 10. Pressure coefficient distribution along the airfoil chord; trailing edge zone highlighted in yellow.

The lift coefficient corresponding to these conditions required a high incidence of about 14° . At this incidence, RANS simulations returned a completely separated flow. Therefore, Euler computations were performed because providing an attached flow allowed to reach such a high CL . This approach is conservative for the determination of loads because the C_p of the attached flow in the zone of the flap yields higher results with respect to a separated flow. The Xfoil results are shown in Figure 10 only for comparison. It is worth noting that the morphed flap was designed by employing a RANS code with the Spalart–Allmaras turbulence model.

5. Optimization Results

This section is devoted to the results of the optimization process.

In Figure 11, the evolution of the normalized maximum fitness against the iteration is presented for the best six configurations. As is evident, the algorithm arrives at a stable convergence within 150 cycles with a maximum improvement of about 25% with respect to the initial condition.

Figure 11. Fitness evolution vs. iteration.

The following criteria were adopted to evaluate the following configurations:

$$\text{Buckling absorption} : |\lambda - 1|. \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Dynamic performance} : (\omega - 40 \text{ Hz})/40 \text{ Hz}. \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Load absorption} : 1 - \sigma_{max}/(200 \text{ MPa}). \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Actuation force} : 1 - F_{act}/(1500 \text{ N}). \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Actuation stroke} : 1 - \text{stroke}/(60 \text{ mm}). \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Lightness} : 1 - \text{weight}/(10 \text{ kg}). \quad (6)$$

The first three criteria are directly linked to the definition of the fitness function whose final value does not depend only on the deviation from the target but also on stability, dynamic, and load absorption performance. The other three criteria instead take into account the needed actuation force and stroke and the total weight of the structure. The reference force and stroke, 1500 N and 60 mm, were chosen on the basis of the performance typically required by an actuator for this type of application and in compliance with the requirements discussed in the previous section. Finally, the reference weight of 10 kg was defined on the basis of the weight of the corresponding requirement of 22 kg/m or, for the 0.5 spanned flap, 11 kg.

The parameters relevant to the criteria were computed and are reported for all the six configurations in Table 2. Then, Formulas (1)–(6) were implemented and the outcomes organized into the spider map illustrated in Figure 12; this gives a quick perception of the level of fulfilment of the different criteria.

Table 2. Performance of the best configurations.

Configuration ID	Buckling First Eigenvalue	1st Frequency (Hz)	Safety Margin	Actuator Force (N)	Actuator Stroke (mm)	Weight (kg)
1	−2.58	49.12	0.76	2687.26	50.10	4.29
2	−1.75	49.12	0.79	2741.70	49.86	4.33
3	−2.62	50.15	0.84	2702.69	48.80	4.37
4	−2.75	51.22	0.85	2819.29	48.62	4.51
5	−1.90	50.11	0.83	2767.96	48.64	4.41
6	−2.47	48.40	0.82	2643.47	48.69	4.23

Figure 12. Criteria of evaluation vs. configurations.

The 4th configuration (yellow) seems clearly the least uniform, as it is particularly dramatically penalized in terms of lightness. The 2nd configuration (orange) is uniform but shows performance results lower than the others. Configuration 5 (light blue) is similar: uniform but with low performance. The 6th configuration (green) exhibits the highest performance. Similarly, configuration 1 (dark blue) exhibits high performance for all the criteria but dynamic. Finally, configuration 3 (grey) seems uniform and at the same time offers moderately high performance. Figure 13 gives a view of this layout in clean configuration (blue line) and under full actuation with and without external loads (cyan and red). The results are also compared with the target morphed shape (green). A summary of the main features is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Parameters of the selected configuration.

Parameter	Parameter Description	Value
P ₁	Actuator forward hinge—abscissa	−0.250 m
P ₂	Actuator forward hinge—ordinate	0.084 m
P ₃	Top connection node of the web	72
P ₄	Bottom connection node of the web	173
P ₅	Web thickness	0.0027 m
P ₆	Upper skin thickness—forward region	0.0028 m

Table 3. Cont.

Parameter	Parameter Description	Value
P ₇	Upper skin thickness—rearward region	0.0021 m
P ₈	Lower skin thickness—forward region	0.0028 m
P ₉	Lower skin thickness—rearward region	0.0021 m
P ₁₀	Upper skin extension—forward region	33.7%
P ₁₁	Lower skin extension—forward region	39.6%

Figure 13. Configuration 3: target morphed shape (green); clean configuration (blue); fully actuated with and without aerodynamic loads (cyan and red).

6. Refined Model and Result Evaluation

Once the best compromise was identified, a refined FE model was developed to verify the outcomes of the optimization process. The scope of this model was both to validate the predictions of the optimization approach and to determine details that cannot be covered by the coarse model, as the actuation chain acts on more regions: the stress variation along the span, stress level, and distribution at some interfaces.

In line with the selected layout (configuration 3), for the upper skin, thickness values of 2.84 and 2.11 mm were set for the front and rear regions, respectively, with the transition at 34% of the entire length of the panel. In the same way, for the lower skin, thickness values of 2.84 and 2.13 mm were assumed for the front and rear regions, with a transition at 40%. Finally, the thickness of the web was set at 2.74 mm. The refined digital mock-up is illustrated in Figure 14, while the relevant FE model and the main features are reported in Figure 15 and Table 4. A central flange is fixed on the lower skin at mid-span. On its upper part, there is a pin to which one edge of the actuator is connected. To assure a uniform transmission in span-wise direction of the forces and displacements produced by the actuator, two transversal bars were used to connect the central flange to the left and right sides of the lower panel. The same bars are also exploited to join the lateral flanges to the sliding tracks. All the parts are made of 7075-T6 aluminum alloy [48] except the two bars and the actuator hinge pin, which are made of UHSS [51].

Figure 14. Refined digital mock-up of the compliant trailing edge: lateral view (a) and isometric view (b).

Figure 15. Refined FE model (a) and detail of the transmission chain (b).

Table 4. Main features of the refined FE model.

Feature	Value
Number of nodes	125,055
Number of elements	524,666
Extension along the chord	0.53 m
Width	0.5 m
Upper skin material	7075-T6 aluminum alloy
Lower skin material	7075-T6 aluminum alloy
Web material	Kinematics bars
	alloySteel
Thickness distribution for the upper skin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.84 mm, front portion • 2.11 mm, rear portion
Thickness transition on the upper skin	34% of skin length in chord
Thickness distribution for the lower skin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.84 mm, front portion • 2.13 mm, rear portion
Thickness transition on the lower skin	40% of skin length in chord

The skin is modeled using square CQUAD [52] elements with a characteristic length of 1 mm both in chord and span-wise directions, while the mechanism components (flanges, sliding tracks, actuator hinge pin, and bars) are modeled by 3D CTETRA [53] elements. RBE2 [49] elements were used to connect the flanges to the skin, the bars, and the actuator pin to the flanges and the sliding tracks.

At first, a static analysis was performed actuating the morphing trailing edge with and without the aerodynamic loads. The results are presented in terms of displacement (deformed shape and maximum displacement printed in the caption) and stress level (contour map and relevant color bar) for the actuation alone (Figure 16a) and in combination with the aerodynamic loads (Figure 16b). The aerodynamic loads diminish the vertical displacement of the trailing edge, which passes from 0.139 to 0.132 m. Their impact in terms of stress is remarkable, passing from a maximum value of 162 MPa for the actuation alone to 193 MPa when the aerodynamic loads also act on the structure. This value is well below the ultimate stress limit of the aluminum alloy (572 MPa [48]). Finally, the force required by the actuator passes from 833 to 1293 N in the presence of the aerodynamic loads. Finally, the weight of the structure, including the actuation, was 8.85 kg.

A modal analysis was then addressed. The 1st modal shape, corresponding to a frequency of 45.2 Hz, is represented in Figure 17a; in the same figure, the next two modes are also illustrated (93 Hz and 96 Hz—Figure 17a,b). The displacements illustrated in these plots were suitably magnified to better highlight the details of the modal shapes. Finally, a buckling analysis was also carried out, yielding an eigenvalue of -17.3 . The maximum stress level, the 1st modal frequency, and the 1st buckling eigenvalue are compliant with the constraints assumed for the optimization process.

A comparison was organized among the outcomes of the simplified and refined models. All the values, relevant deviations, and % errors are reported in Table 5. The simplified model proved to be slightly more conservative from a structural point of view: the stress level, the buckling eigenvalues, and the frequency were a little bit closer to the thresholds discussed in the previous section. In terms of displacement, the refined model yielded a slightly smaller prediction (2 mm less) of the vertical displacement of the trailing edge. The two models, in any case, appear in good agreement with an exception on the buckling eigenvalue, where the tridimensional feature makes the difference in terms of global absorption of the loads.

Table 5. Comparison of the outcomes of the simplified and refined FE models.

Comparison Term	Simplified Model	Refined Model	Deviation	Error
Trailing edge vertical displacement	0.140 m	0.138 m	−0.002 m	−1.45%
Max von Mises stress	200 MPa	193 MPa	−7 MPa	−3.63%
1st buckling eigenvalue	−17.3	−30	−12.7	+42%
1st modal frequency	45.2 Hz	46.7 Hz	+1.5	+3.21%

(a)

(b)

Figure 16. Results of the static analysis: displacement field (morphed shape and maximum displacement printed in the caption) and stress distribution (contour map and relevant color bar) under the actuation of the loads alone (a) and in combination with the aerodynamic loads (b).

Figure 17. First modal shape of the refined FE model (a) and second and third modal shapes (b,c); the displacements illustrated in these plots were suitably magnified to better highlight the details of the modal shapes.

7. Results vs. Requirements

In this section, the main achievements of the work are discussed against the requirements.

The philosophy at the basis of the morphed trailing edge is compliant with the preservation of the laminar flow in cruise, with a consequent reduction in the aerodynamic drag. What is also significant is the placement of the actuation system, which is entirely housed within the available space of the wing box, contributing to a cleaner wing in cruise. All these aspects are in line with the first requirement at the A/C level (enhanced aerodynamic performance).

Differently from a conventional flap, the actuation must bear not only the external aerodynamic loads but also the elastic reaction of the structure. This is a penalty that generally characterizes compliant devices. However, the optimization addressed in this work kept the maximum actuation load within a value of 1293 N for the 0.5 m spanned flap, which is lower than the requirement (1500 N). A rough estimate of the impact on the weight of the actuator can be obtained by the empiric formula that links the actuator force, F_{act} , to its weight, W_{act} [54]:

$$W_{act} = F_{act}^{0.5} \tag{7}$$

As a result, a weight saving of over 7% with respect to the requirement was observed. Moreover, the optimization of the morphing device as a whole (actuation included) led to a total weight of 8.85 kg that, scaled to 1 m span, corresponds to 17.7 kg/m against the requirement of 22 kg/m, with a net saving of about 19.5%.

The geometry and the materials of the parts were chosen to reduce as much as possible the integration and the maintenance efforts and improve the reliability level. The skin, made of aluminum alloy sheets, can be cut, milled, and bent by means of conventional

operations. The same is true for the web. The connection can be obtained by conventional riveting or structural bonding. The kinematic chain can be also easily built through conventional manufacturing operations, and its integration requires a simple assembly rig, given the small number of parts (the transmission arm and the flanges of connection to the bottom skin). This dramatically reduces the number of operations and the complexity of the required tools, with remarkable advantages with respect to a conventional flap characterized by a more complex architecture. However, the sliding part of the skin is worthy of particular attention; the driving tracks represent, in fact, a criticality not in terms of fabrication and material reliability but for the interface and based on bearings, whose inspection and replacement involves a region of the wing box. In this case, a dedicated procedure must be defined to have an easy access to the region, considering removable panels on the lower part of the wing box. This solution must obviously also encompass the replacement of the actuators. But, once again, despite the necessity of accessing the wing box, as the involved interfaces are fewer than in a conventional flap, maintenance advantages can still be conferred.

Figure 18 illustrates the lift coefficient for different configurations computed in the assumption of flow 2D; the two highest ones were computed through the Eulerian hypothesis and thus do not take into account any separation. The highest of them refers to the target morphed shape and the other one to configuration 3. The cluster of the lowest curves was computed by means of the SU2 open-source RANS code [45]; this type of analysis cannot determine the exact maximum lift coefficient but provides the trend in the presence of separation. These lines, corresponding to configurations 1–5, were about 0.3 points below the mid-curve computed through the same method and referring to the target morphed shape. The Eulerian curves indicate the lift coefficient is potentially obtainable by implementing a flow control strategy that minimizes the separation. To compare these curves with the requirements, the $C_{L,MAX}$ values reported in Section 2 and obtained by 3D analyses must be scaled by a factor of 1.25, passing from 2.6 and 2.8 to 2.9 and 3.5, respectively. The just-mentioned scaling factor was estimated through an engineering method and confirmed by a 3D Navier–Stokes simulation [45]. Only the two uppermost curves match the highest of these requirements ($C_{L,MAX} = 3.5$, red line), highlighting the need for a flow control technology.

Finally, in Table 6, a summary of the impact of the proposed technology is provided.

Table 6. Impact of technology.

Effect	Justification
Improvement of the aerodynamic performance	Thanks to the compliant feature, there are no <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaps and/or steps in cruise condition • External flap track fairings
Reduction in the weight	The structural optimization led to a light and efficient load-bearing structure, actuatable by a smaller actuator
Reduction in the maintenance effort	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The simple layout of the device favors inspection and maintenance operations • The low stress level contributes to a more extended operational life
Reduction in take-off and landing distance	Both weight reduction and increase in maximum lift coefficient contribute to this performance

Figure 18. Lift coefficient vs. AoA vs. configuration vs. reference: Eulerian curves for the target morphed shape (black □) and configuration 3 (black □); RANS curves of the target morphed shape (black o) and for configurations 1–5 (colored o); most severe requirement ($C_{L,MAX}$ in landing, red).

It is at this point worth recalling that the aerodynamic requirements were formulated in terms of CL_{max} . The most demanding requirement is in landing conditions, where the CL_{max} has an impact through the touch-down velocity, which scales with the square root of the lift coefficient. Then, the landing distance depends on many other factors and the drag coefficient between them. The drag coefficient of a morphed configuration is expected to be higher with respect to a slot configuration. A potential non-fulfilment of the target CL_{max} would impact the landing distance through the square root of the ΔCL and could be mitigated by the drag coefficient of the morphed configuration.

The drag coefficient was also taken into account in the design process of the morphed configuration. The goal was to limit the separation in the region of the flap. Indeed, the chosen configuration presents the lowest drag coefficient between a range of candidates with similar high-lift coefficients.

8. Conclusions and Further Steps

This study focused on the research and optimization of a compliant trailing edge architecture that generates high lift in cooperation with a droop nose system and a flow control strategy. The device, in particular its smooth geometry, was conceived to adequately support take-off and landing phases and, at the same time, avoid any disturbance in clean configuration and in this way preserving cruise performance. The system was conceived for a strut-braced wing of a next-generation hybrid electric regional aircraft, driving the following stage of the advanced design of the same device. The authors implemented a multi-step design approach on the basis of the experience gained on previous architectures

already considered for the project. The layout was optimized with the aim of approaching a prescribed morphed shape conceived to achieve the desired maximum lift coefficient level. As a result, a structure with an effective load-bearing capability was determined, with benefits in terms of stress level and force required by the actuation system.

All these aspects favorably contribute to the requirements that form the basis of this study:

- Enhanced aerodynamic performance in cruise due to the absence of any geometrical asperities and flap track fairings;
- Reduced weight, as both the trailing edge structure and the actuation are lighter;
- Abatement of maintenance costs and extended operational life due to greater ease of inspection and a well-distributed load;
- Smaller take-off and landing distances, assured by an adequate maximum lift coefficient and by the reduction in weight.

The above achievements and the finalization of the advanced design of the system pave the way for the next steps of the project:

- Definition of a dedicated test campaign for testing on the ground. The test plan will include functional validation under the most severe load conditions, static tests to verify the capability of the structure of absorbing loads without any damage, and dynamic characterization to exclude any potential coupling problem with the wing structure;
- Manufacturing of a full-sized prototype of the trailing edge segment and preparation of the test setup and test rig;
- Execution of the ground tests and assessment of the results.

The previously mentioned activities are in line with the target of the project of maturing this concept up to TRL 5.

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Acronyms and Symbols

A/C	Aircraft
ACTE	Adaptive compliant trailing edge
AoA	Angle of attack
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CL	Lift coefficient
CLEEN	Continuous Lower Energy, Emissions, and Noise
C_L	Lift coefficient
$C_{L,MAX}$	Maximum lift coefficient
D	Deviation between the target morphed shape and the current one
DOF	Degree of freedom
EAP	Electric aircraft propulsion
EMA	Electro-mechanical actuation
f_D	Factor weighting the deviation from the target morphed shape
f_λ	Factor weighting the buckling performance layout
f_s	Factor weighting the stress level of the current layout
f_ω	Factor weighting the modal frequency of the current layout
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
F_{act}	Actuation force
FE	Finite element
FEM	Finite element model
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HER	Hybrid electric regional
HERA	Hybrid electric regional aircraft
HERWINGT	Hybrid Electric Regional Wing Integration Novel Wing Technologies
KTAS	Knots true airspeed
λ	1st buckling eigenvalue
LDO	Leonardo S.p.A.—Aircraft Division
LE	Leading edge
LoD	Lift over drag
MAS	Morphing aircraft structures
NA	Not applicable
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
P_{1-11}	Optimization parameters
PoliMi	Politecnico of Milan
RANS	Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes
s	Curvilinear abscissa
σ_{max}	Max von Mises stress
TE	Trailing edge
TLAR	Top-level aircraft requirements
TRL	Technology readiness level
TUD	Technical University of Delft
UHSS	Ultra-high-strength steel
ω	1st normal frequency

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